
**EVALUATION OF THE PEARL S. BUCK FOUNDATION-PHILIPPINES (PSBP)-
GORDON COLLEGE (GC) NATIONAL SERVICE TRAINING PROGRAM
(NSTP) TUTORIAL PROGRAM**

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the Pearl S. Buck Foundation, Philippines (PSBP) and Gordon College (GC) National Service Training Program (NSTP) Tutorial Program. It employed the quantitative research method with 345 respondents, including tutors, tutees, and program implementers. The findings of the study were the following: The majority of the tutor-respondents are in the 17-18 years old age group, female, single, residing in Olongapo City, are non-indigenous persons, studying at the college level, and tutored the English subject for most (three years) of the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program. The majority of the tutee-respondents are in the 12-13 years old age group, female, single, residing in Olongapo City, are non-indigenous persons, studying at the elementary level, and were taught in both English and Math subjects during the five years of the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program. The majority of the implementer-respondents are in the 21-25 years old age group, female, single, residing in Olongapo City, are non-indigenous persons at the college level, and were involved in the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program for one semester. Based on the findings also, the indicators with the highest mean rating, 4.0, or “achieved beyond expectation,” vis-à-vis requirements expected from PSBP and GC-NSTP are as follows: “conducts pre-test and post-test to all children;” “provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents, and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions;” “awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children;” “awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program;” and “provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program.” Ultimately, the researchers suggested some vital recommendations based on the study results.

Keywords: Pearl S Buck Foundation-Philippines (PSBP), National Service Training Program (NSTP), Community Service, Evaluation Study, Tutorial Program

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INTRODUCTION

Republic Act 9163, or the National Service Training Program (NSTP) Act of 2001, is a required program for college students. It has been implemented at Gordon College (GC) through the Civic Welfare and Training Service (CWTS) and the Literacy Training Service (LTS) components since 2012. In partnership with Gordon College, the Pearl S. Buck Foundation Philippines (PSBP) has implemented the PSBP and GC-NSTP Tutorial Program for seven years.

This program has continually benefitted more than 100 sponsored children since its inception. They come from poor and/or indigenous families in Olongapo City and Subic, Zambales. According to the partnership agreement, PSBP identifies and selects indigent children based on criteria. On the other hand, Gordon College students of the NSTP tutor these children based on preferred subjects through the supervision of a coordinator and instruction from faculty.

The LTS component is significant because it addresses the problems in education identified in the Sustainable Development Goals from 2016-2030 (SDG, undated). In the Philippines, cohort survival was between 73-75% at the elementary level and 78-79% at the secondary level (DepEd, 2016).

Like any other program of higher education institutions (HEIs), summative evaluations facilitate continuous improvements, including duplication of good practices that may be identified. This is especially critical in light of reduced funding and resources for public education institutions, including non-profit organizations, competitions brought about by an increasing number of schools and modes of learning, and standards required of graduates.

NSTP aims to provide voluntary services to ensure and sustain Philippine development. According to a PISA (2012) study, girls' performance improves when they see themselves positively. In another study, an additional year of learning translates to increased income, improved health, and improved service to the community (Baum et al., 2010).

An evaluation of the PSBP and GC-NSTP Tutorial Program is significant because it could improve the output of sponsored children in their English and Math subjects and sustain the partnership for this program. The NSTP provides a venue by which GC becomes relevant as a local community college.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to evaluate the implementation of the GC NSTP and PSBP Tutorial Program from 2013-2017.

The specific questions of the study are as follows:

- 1) How may the profile of the program stakeholders be described in terms of the following:
 - 1.1) age;
 - 1.2) sex;
 - 1.3) civil status;
 - 1.4) residence;

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- 1.5) ethnicity;
 - 1.6) highest educational attainment;
 - 1.7) number of year/s and subjects involved in the Tutorial Program; and
 - 1.8) number of semesters of involved in the Tutorial Program?
- 2) How may the program be evaluated in terms of the achievement of requirements of the agreement as expected from:
 - 2.2) GC-NSTP; and
 - 2.3) PSBP?
 - 3) What is the implication of the findings to the sustainability of the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research team used the quantitative design of research evaluation of the Pearl S. Buck Foundation- Philippines (PSBP)- Gordon College (GC)- National Service Training Program (NSTP) Tutorial Program implemented from 2012 to 2017.

Quantitative Research is used to quantify the problem by generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. It is used to quantify attitudes, opinions, behaviors, and other defined variables – and generalize results from a larger sample population. Quantitative Research uses measurable data to formulate facts and uncover patterns in research. Quantitative data collection methods are much more structured than Qualitative data collection methods. Quantitative data collection methods include various forms of surveys – online surveys, paper surveys, mobile surveys and kiosk surveys, face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, longitudinal studies, website interceptors, online polls, and systematic observations (De Franzo, 2011).

Respondents

The respondents are the following stakeholders of the PSBP-GC-NSTP Tutorial Program: the NSTP students (tutors), sponsored children (tutees), and personnel- implementers of PSBP and GC. There were one-hundred-ninety (190) tutors, one-hundred-sixteen (116) tutees, twenty-nine (29) GC and ten (10) PSBP implementers- with a total number of three-hundred-and-forty-five (345) respondents who answered the survey-questionnaire for the Evaluation of the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program.

Purposeful sampling of respondents was conducted. They are specifically key informants who were directly involved in the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program. The researchers contacted the respondents offline and online. Tutors – some already graduates- who responded positively were included as respondents.

Instrument of the Study

The study evaluated the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP)-Gordon College (GC) National Service Training Program (NSTP) Tutorial Program. It utilized a survey questionnaire using a Likert Scale. A draft survey questionnaire was submitted to two research experts in the college for critique.

Researchers also conducted document analysis. The survey questionnaire was used to describe whether the requirements of the agreement were achieved. Meanwhile, document analysis was used to verify provisions of the contract, i.e. regarding the requirements expected to be achieved by both PSBP and GC-NSTP. An unstructured interview was conducted to verify the implementation of the said program and analysis of the findings.

Statistical Analysis

The data was organized and processed through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The following statistical techniques employed answered the specific questions of the study. In the data presentation, frequency distribution, percentage distribution, and mean distribution were computed.

In interpreting the averages of the rating regarding the requirements of the agreement expected to be achieved by both the PSBP and GC NSTP, the following scale with descriptive rating was adopted:

<i>Nominal</i>	<i>Range of Scale</i>	<i>Description</i>
4	3.36-4.0	Achieved beyond expectation
3	2.51-3.25	Achieved as targeted
2	1.76-2.50	Moderately achieved as targeted
1	1.00-1.75	Not achieved as targeted

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary purpose of this study is to evaluate the Pearl S. Buck Foundation Philippines and Gordon College (GC) National Service Training Program (NSTP) Tutorial Program.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutor-Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-16 years old	78	41.05
17-18 years old	84	44.21
19-20 years old	11	5.78
21-25 years old	9	4.73
Above 25 years old	8	4.21
Total	190	100

Table 1 shows that out of one hundred (190) tutor-respondents, there are: 78 (or 41.05%) from the age group 15-16 years old, 84 (or 44.21%) from the age group 17-18 years old, 11 (or 5.78%) from the age group 19-20 years old; 9 (or 4.73%) from the 21-25 age group; and 8 (or 4.21%) from the age group above 25 years old.

Table 1 shows that most tutors come from the 17–18-year-old age group, which is not far from the frequency distribution of the 15-16 age group. Both groups are the ages of a typical first-year student when the National Service Training Program (NSTP) must be

taken. NSTP subjects are required general elective subjects offered earlier than core competency subjects.

Republic Act 9163, or the NSTP Act, ensures that a sense of nationhood is ingrained relatively early in students' minds, guiding them to protect and later pursue careers that help contribute towards the country's sustainability. Natividad (2016) reported that 98% of youth today needed to contribute to community development and that 26% would like “to be remembered as a person who has changed the world.” The number of millennials is critical because, as Natividad (2016) found, 72% of the global workforce will be millennials by 2025.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutor-Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	112	58.94
Male	78	41.05
Total	190	100

Table 2 shows that out of 190 tutor respondents, 112 (58.94%) are female, and 78 (41.05%) are male. This shows that the majority of the tutor-respondents are female. Statistics in 2017 show that more girls than boys enroll in college (PSA), specifically 2.2 million, as opposed to 1.8 million, respectively. This is most likely because boys are expected to provide for their families. Therefore, instead of finishing school, they try to find gainful employment. Gyonos (2011) longitudinal study provided data on the reasons and consequences of school leaving (whether at the primary, secondary, or tertiary level) in the European Union (EU). It found a “strong relationship between the variables named participation in education and early school leaving; more than that, there is a strong relationship between the extent of school studies completion and the unemployment rate.” However, what is important about this study is that an inverse relationship between participation in education and unemployment was found. This means the employment rate decreased when participation in education increased. Programs to ensure that both males and females drop out and return to school are needed to address this issue.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutor-Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	188	98.94
Married	2	10.52
Total	190	100

Table 3 shows that out of 190 tutor respondents, 188 (or 98.94%) are single, and 2 (or 10.52%) are married. This shows that the majority of the respondents are single. Societal expectation from students (especially first year) is that their education, rather than having their own family, should be a priority for them. Two foci of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals for 2030- inclusive and quality education and gender equality and

empowerment- highlight the importance of this (Philippine Commission on Women, 2020).

Statistics in 2013, however, show that among 15-19-year-old girls, one in ten are already mothers or are pregnant at the time. This is despite the devolution of health services in the local government units through enacting the Local Government Code in 1992 and the passage of the Responsible Parenthood and Reproductive Health Act in 2012 (Lawphil, 2012). However, what is ironic about this is that data shows that more females are now going to college. ASEAN figures show that the gender gap has closed since the 1960s (ASEAN, 2016). Studying and earning money for a family may be difficult for a young student, so married life might be less inviting for them.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutor-Respondents in Terms of Residence

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Olongapo City	101	53.15
Zambales	64	33.68
Bataan	25	13.15
Total	190	100

Table 4 shows that out of the total of 190 tutors, 101 (or 53.15%) are from Olongapo City, 64 (or 33.68%) are from Zambales, and 25 (or 13.15%) are from Bataan. This means that the majority of the respondents reside in Olongapo City.

Gordon College (GC) is a local college subsidized by the city government of Olongapo and operating in the same area. It was established to help develop the community of Olongapo, being a community college. Olongapo student-residents are provided scholarships. The majority of the student populace of GC are scholars. The provision of scholarships, the track record of the college (in terms of percentage of licensure board examination passers), and accessibility may explain the high number of tutor-respondents from the city.

A study shows that community colleges have also been able to contribute to local economies by way of workforce development and training (Swanger, 2013). According to the same author, these are also in other areas, such as innovations, research, small business development, building livable communities, and buying local produce.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutors in terms of Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
Indigenous	0	0
Non-indigenous	190	100
Total	190	100

Table 5 shows that out of the 190 total number of tutor-respondents, there is no indigenous person. The country comprises several indigenous groups, including Region III, where Olongapo City is located. The National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) estimates that there are 14M IPs in the country (See, 2021). Seven provinces

comprise Region III, and Aytas are found in Zambales, Pampanga, Nueva Ecija, and Bataan.

Indigenous peoples/communities are those who, from time immemorial, have been able to preserve their culture (IPRA Law). However, while the law mandates support for the education of IPs, only some can finish college education less go to formal school.

In 2016, the elementary-level completion rate was 92.7%, dropping to 82.4% at the high school level (PSA, 2018). In 2015, Rappler (Rodriguez, 2016) reported that according to PSA, one in ten Filipinos aged 6-24 was out of school.

The chances of marginalized students, including IPs, are even less. Shapiro et al. (2017) found that among US college students in 2010, “54.8 percent completed a degree or certificate within six years of entering a postsecondary institution. However, broken down by race and ethnicity, those rates fluctuate by up to 25 percent. White and Asian students completed their programs at similar rates 62 percent and 63.2 percent, respectively -- while Hispanic and black students graduated at 45.8 percent and 38 percent, respectively.”

Poverty and marginalization explain this phenomenon. Including an IP as a tutor would significantly boost both IP and non-IP tutees. At the school level, the PISA (2012) study shows that disadvantaged schools can improve their performance. PISA reported that “the highest-performing school systems allocate educational resources more equitably among advantaged and disadvantaged schools and grant more autonomy over curricula and assessments to individual schools. A belief that all students can achieve at a high level and a willingness to engage all stakeholders in education – including students, through such channels as seeking student feedback on teaching practices – are hallmarks of successful school systems.”

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutor-Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
High School graduate	0	0
College level	190	100
College Graduate	0	0
Total:	190	100

The NSTP Law requires that college students take two subjects- NSTP 101 and NSTP 102. This means that subjects are not offered at the high school or any other level. Gordon College has only recently offered the Senior High School (SHS) Program; NSTP is not a subject taken up by SHS students.

Section 4 of the Revised Internal Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act 9163 provides that “All incoming freshmen students, male and female, starting School Year (SY) 2002-2003, enrolled in any baccalaureate and at least two (2) year technical-vocational or associate courses, are required to complete one (1) NSTP component of their choice, as a graduation requirement.”

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutor-Respondents in terms of

Years and Subject involved in the NSTP Tutorial Program

Subject	Year	%	Total	%								
	2013		2014		2015		2016		2017			
English	29	15.26					33	17.36	45	23.68	107	56.31
Math			35	18.42	48	25.26					83	43.69
Total											190	100

Table 7 shows that only two subjects- English and Math- are taught under the NSTP Tutorial Program- i.e., through the partnership between Gordon College and the Pearl S. Buck Foundation, Philippines. The English subject was taught by NSTP tutor-students in the years 2013 (29 students or 15.26%), 2016 (33 students or 17.36%), and 2017 (45 students or 23.68%).

On the other hand, Math was taught in two years in the five years, i.e., between 2013-2017: by 35 students (or 18.42%) and by 48 students (or 25.26%) and of the 190 total population of NSTP tutor-respondents, 107 (or 56.31%) taught English while 83 (or 43.69%) NSTP tutor-respondents taught Math. This shows that the majority, or 56.31%, of the respondents were tutored in the English language.

Studies by different research groups show the importance of communication and problem-solving skills in the 21st century (Envision, undated). A mismatch between graduate competencies and workplace requirements has been noted. Morallo (2018) states, “English proficiency level of college graduates in the Philippines is lower than the proficiency target set for high school students in Thailand and the competency requirement for taxi drivers in Dubai.”

The tutorial program aims to address this gap. The Gordon College National Service Training Program (NSTP) is a partner of the PSBP through the Literacy Training Service (LTS) component. The contract provides that through this program, indigent children from communities are tutored in Mathematics and English subjects by NSTP students or tutors.

Results show that 18 indicators were agreed upon and that GC-NSTP must comply with them. Of the 18 requirements, 13 (or 72.22%) had an adjectival rating of “achieved beyond expectation” or a numerical rating of between 3.36-4.0.

These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: “recruits its best NSTP students to participate for the Tutorial Program (3.65)”; “provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program (3.76)”; “leads the orientation of its NSTP teachers concerning the Tutorial Program (3.77)”; “focuses the tutorial sessions on enhancing the children’s English/Math skills” (3.55); “leads the matching of children and tutors applying the 1:1 ratio” (3.94); “provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors” (3.97); “conducts pre-test and post-test to all children-participants” (4.0); “leads in the identification of appropriate tutorial approach for each sponsored child using the results of pre-test and data in report cards” (3.78); “discuss the outcome of analysis and identify approaches to the NSTP tutors” (3.68); “ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance” (3.65); “requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter’s sponsors” (3.36); “ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home” (3.97); and,

“requires the NSTP tutors to submit a one-page book review of the ‘Good Earth’ to PSBP” (3.88).

Table 8. Mean Rating of the Requirements of the Agreement as expected from Gordon College- National Service Training Program (GC-NSTP), According to the Tutor-Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Recruits its best NSTP students to participate for the Tutorial Program	3.65	Achieved beyond expectation
2. Provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program	3.76	Achieved beyond expectation
3. Leads the orientation of its NSTP teachers concerning the tutorial program.	3.77	Achieved beyond expectation
4. Focuses the tutorial sessions on enhancing the children’s English/Math skills.	3.55	Achieved beyond expectation
5. Leads in the preparation of assessment tools (Pre- test and post-test that will be used in monitoring and evaluation of academic competency of sponsored children and in identifying tutorial approaches.	3.22	Achieved as targeted
6. Leads the matching of children and tutors applying the 1:1 ratio	3.94	Achieved beyond expectation
7. Provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors	3.97	Achieved beyond expectation
8. Conducts pre- test and post-test to all children participants	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
9. Leads in the identification of appropriate tutorial approach for each sponsored child using the results of pre-test and data in report cards	3.78	Achieved beyond expectation
10. Discuss the outcome of analysis and identify approaches to the NSTP tutors	3.68	Achieved beyond expectation
11. Ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance	3.65	Achieved beyond expectation
12. Requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter’s sponsors	3.36	Achieved beyond expectation
13. Ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home.	3.97	Achieved beyond expectation
14. Requires the NSTP tutors to submit a one-page book review of the “Good Earth” to PSBP	3.88	Achieved beyond expectation
15. Ensures that the tutors will discuss “The Good Earth” to the children.	2.88	Achieved as targeted
16. Requires all tutors to participate in the Quiz Bee concerning the life and works of Pearl S. Buck	2.83	Achieved as targeted
17. Leads the evaluation of the Tutorial Program and submit a report to PSBP	2.65	Achieved as targeted
18. Provides technical inputs in the compliance of the different documentary requisites of the course.	3.27	Achieved beyond expectation
Overall Mean	3.55	Achieved beyond expectation

Of the 18 requirements, 5 (or 27.78 %) had an adjectival rating of “achieved as targeted” or a mean rating of 2.65-3.27. These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows:

“leads in the preparation of assessment tools. Pre-test and post-test that will be used in monitoring and evaluation of academic competency of sponsored children and in identifying tutorial approaches” (3.22); “ensure that the tutors will discuss “ The Good Earth” to the children” (2.88); “requires all tutors to participate in the Quiz Bee concerning the life and works of Pearl S. Buck” (2.83); “leads the evaluation of the Tutorial Program and submit a report to PSBP” (2.65); “provides technical inputs in the compliance of the different documentary requisites of the course” (3.27).

The requirement with the highest mean rating, 4.0 or “achieved beyond expectation,” is “Conducts pre-test and post-test to all children.” Both pre-tests and post-tests provide the program with data showing whether the tutees learned well or less. This may imply that this strategy is effective and that the protocol for administering the tests was observed well. Chiang et al. (2015) define reliability as the “consistency of a measure,” while validity “is the extent to which the scores from a measure represent the variable they are intended to.”

Requirements with “achieved beyond expectation” ratings are generally related to instruction. Instruction involves the preparation, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of activities related to the teaching of subjects assigned. GC instructor competencies and attitudes are measured through a 360-degree evaluation by students, peers, and supervisors to ensure that objectives are achieved.

The big number (13 out of 18 requirements), showing an “achievement beyond expectation” rating, shows the faculty's ability to meet the requirements of instruction, specifically on the administration of tests, for the said program.

Table 9. Mean Rating of the Requirements from Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP), According to the Tutor-Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Assist GC in the orientation of NSTP teachers and students	3.81	Achieved beyond expectation
2. Gives initial orientation to children and parents regarding the Tutorial Program	3.65	Achieved beyond expectation
3. Requires all sponsored children to submit two copies of their report cards for the 1 st and 2 nd semesters	2.54	Achieved as targeted
4. Provides GC a copy of the children's report card	2.54	Achieved as targeted
5. Provides the library/NSTP department of GC with copies of “The Good Earth” novel.	3.81	Achieved beyond expectation
6. Monitors all tutorial sessions and ensure the safety of the NSTP students and the sponsored children.	3.87	Achieved beyond expectation
7. Provides all sponsored children, parents and NSTP tutors during the tutorial sessions	3.38	Achieved beyond expectation
8. Provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
9. Provides transportation to all sponsored children and parents	3.94	Achieved beyond expectation
10. Assists the college in the evaluation of the Tutorial Program.	3.95	Achieved beyond expectation

11. Awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children.	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
12. Awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
13. Provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program.	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
14. Prepares feedback forms which will be answered by parents and tutors.	3.95	Achieved beyond expectation
15. Prepares a report based on feedback forms submitted by parents and tutors	3.82	Achieved beyond expectation
16. Submits all reports to the PSBP Board President and to the PSBP International in Pennsylvania USA.	3.90	Achieved beyond expectation
Overall Mean	3.70	Achieved beyond expectation

These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: “assist GC in the orientation of NSTP teachers and students (3.81); “gives initial orientation to children and parents regarding the Tutorial Program (3.65); “provides the library/NSTP department of GC with copies of ‘The Good Earth’ novel (3.81); “monitors all tutorial sessions and sure the safety of the NSTP students and the sponsored children” (3.87); “provides all sponsored children, parents and NSTP tutors during the tutorial sessions” (3.38) ; “provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions” (4.0); “provides transportation to all sponsored children and parents’ (3.94); “assists the college in the evaluation of the Tutorial Program (3.95); “awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children” (4.0); awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program (4.0); “provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program: (4.0); “prepares feedback forms which will be answered by parents and tutors” (3.95); “Prepares a report based on feedback forms submitted by parents and tutors (3.82); and, “Submits all reports to the PSBP Board President and to the PSBP International in Pennsylvania USA” (3.9).

Of the 16 requirements, 2 (or 22.50%) had an adjectival rating of “achieved as targeted” or a numerical mean rating of 2.54 for both indicators. These requirements and the numerical mean rating are as follows: “requires all sponsored children to submit two copies of their report cards for the 1st and 2nd semesters” (2.54); and “provides GC a copy of the children’s report card” (2.54).

The requirements with the highest mean rating, 4.0 or “achieved beyond expectation,” are as follows: “Provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions;” “Awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children;” “Awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program;” and “Provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program.”

All four requirements imply the need for food and recognition. While Maslow’s hierarchy of needs shows food as a basic physiological necessity, recognition refers to the need for esteem (Macleod, 2018).

Requirements with “achieved beyond expectation” generally require the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP) to coordinate with its partner organization, Gordon College, the parents, the tutors, and the tutees. Through the Tutorial Program, PSBP is required per contract and is observed to deal with said stakeholders.

Applying a supply chain model of education (Gopalakrishnan, 2015), the program stakeholders may be considered critical elements of both input and process parts. This means that through the elements of the education process, the program proceeds to accomplish its desired output. Overall, the Tutorial Program is expected to improve the tutee’s knowledge, skills, and attitude (KSA) in either English or Math subjects, which are requirements in the primary level and junior high school.

Both input and process allow for the expected output to be achieved. All three are required for education to develop. With 14 out of 16 requirements showing that expectations are achieved beyond the minimum requirement, PSBP’s accomplishments indicate that they are nearer to the goals of the agreed partnership.

Table 10. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
6-7 years old	8	6.89
8-9 years old	21	18.10
10-11 years old	33	28.44
12-13 years old	38	32.75
14-15 years old	15	12.93
15 and above	1	0.86
Total	116	100

Table 10 shows that out of the 116 total number of tutee-respondents, there are 8 (or 6.89%) in the 6-7 age bracket; 21 (or 18.10%) in the 8-9 age bracket; 33 (or 28.44%) in the 10-11 age bracket; 38 (or 32.75%) in the 12-13 age bracket; 15 (or 12.93%) in the 14-15 age bracket; and 1 (or .86%) in the 15 and above age bracket.

Table 10 shows that most tutee-respondents are in the 12–13-year-old bracket.

All these age brackets, from 6-15 and above, are the program's focus- meaning students who are in the primary and junior high school level. This level is critical in a child's development because it is foundational. What is learned or not learned during this period will impact the secondary and tertiary levels.

This is based on the assumption that the child can pursue both upper levels. The World Education News and Reviews (Macha et al., 2018) report that the completion rate (elementary level) was approximately 70% in 2005. The net enrollment rate was 58.5% (secondary level) in the same year.

Table 11. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutees in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	75	64.65
Male	41	35.34
Total	116	100

Table 12 shows that of the total 116 tutee-respondents, 75 (or 64.65%) are female, and 41 (or 35.34%) are male. This data shows that the majority of the respondents are female. Statistics show that after the implementation of the Millennium Development Goals ended in 2015, much has been done in the education sector. There were 57 million who are out of school youth in 2015, and “almost half of the out-of-school girls (48 percent) are unlikely to ever go to school, compared to 37 percent of boys. On the other hand, boys are more likely to leave school early” (United Nations, 2015).

The fact that the tutorial program of PSBP-GC NSTP has more female tutees may facilitate efforts towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of women empowerment in the city. This is because the societal upbringing of daughters is for them to stay at home, be less competitive, and acquire nurturing and submissive qualities (Our Watch, 2018).

Apart from the family as an institution, others –such as religion, media, politics, economics, and culture- reinforce and affirm behaviors that relegate females to secondary and second-class citizen roles. Our Watch’s study of parents with 0–3-year-old children in Australia recommended supporting parents to reinforce gender equality in nurturing children. This is because it was found out that mothers were more inclined to expose their children to “masculine-type of play” than fathers. However, both parents want to be hands-on in the upbringing of their children.

Table 12. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in Terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	116	100
Married	0	0
Total	116	100

Table 12 shows that of the total 116 tutee-respondents, all of them are single (100%), and none of them are married.

This is expected because, based on Table 11, the age range of the tutees is six years old to above fifteen years old, and based on Table 15, tutees are either at the primary or secondary level.

This is the typical age of primary and secondary level students, which implies that whatever socioeconomic status the students are, they are in school. Studies show that some students enter school late in age. Qihui (2017) notes that while a Philippine study shows that late entry “reduces children’s dropout and grade repetition rates in these countries,” in contrast, her study in China reveals that “...a 1-year delay in school entry reduces children’s scores on a cognitive ability test administered when they were aged 9–12.” It was noted that this finding may help to explain school dropout.

Table 13. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in Terms of Residence

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
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Olongapo City	48	41.37
Zambales	28	24.13
Bataan	40	34.48
Total	116	100

Table 13 shows that of the total 116 tutee-respondents, 48 (or 41.37%) reside in Olongapo City, 28 (or 24.13%) are from Zambales, and 40 (or 34.48%) are from Bataan.

Based on this table, the majority come from Olongapo City. This may be expected, considering that accessibility is a factor in determining which school a child goes to. A minor may not be expected to have the capacity to safely navigate around a community/ies that he/she is not familiar with.

Osborne and Gabler (1992) narrate how American entrepreneurial spirit has shaped education in the 1980s. The results showed fewer drop-outs and students who top Scholastic Aptitude Tests (SAT), according to Osborne and Gaebler.

Data shows that there are more private than public schools in the Philippines, although scholarships are available in government schools. The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) lists 112 state universities and colleges (SUCs); 107 local colleges and universities (LCUs); and 1710 private higher education institutions in AY 2016-2017 (CHED, 2017). In Olongapo City, there is only one public college and 12 private higher education institutions listed in the area (Facts and Figures, undated). This only shows that even though the cost of education is high, it continues to be a basic need. That is, even for those who are poor. The Philippine News Agency (April 2018) reports that only 23% of Filipinos finished tertiary education due to poverty.

When a community's poverty threshold is high, it would make more sense to send them to nearby schools (Osborne and Gabler, 1992).

Table 14 shows that of the total 116 tutee-respondents, 6 (or 5.17%) are indigenous persons and 110 (or 94.82%) are non-indigenous.

Olongapo City is considered a melting pot of people from different provinces in the country, because of the employment opportunities that may be found in the urban area. This is, however, a misnomer because the city neither has an agricultural, fishing nor forestry base with which industries may be developed. The result, therefore, is an economy that is dependent on the service sector and a growing population of migrants (Nierras, 2006).

Table 14. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in terms of Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
Indigenous	6	5.17
Non-indigenous	110	94.82
Total	116	100

History reveals that Aytas –indigenous communities found in Central Luzon-used to live inside the Subic Bay Freeport Zone (SBFZ), which used to be a United States Naval

Base. Pushed up by myriad factors, many of them now live in the boondocks- their children sent to schools that are relatively inaccessible. These factors include land-grabbing, legislations and migration of lowlanders. Caballero found out that “. the Aeta Magbukun of Pastolan were issued a CADT [Certificate of Ancestral Domain Title] of almost 4356 ha on 25 March 2004, representing 45% of the Subic Bay Freeport Zone” (MacHenry, 2018). A few of the Ayta children try to pursue education, even if several factors are stacked against them.

Table 15. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
High School level	54	46.55
Elementary level	62	53.44
Total	116	100

Table 15 shows that of the 116 tutee-respondents, 54 (or 46.55%) are at the high school level; and 62 (or 53.44%) are at the elementary level.

Results show that majority are studying at the primary level when they joined the Tutorial Program. Philippine statistics show, at the national and local level, that there are more students enrolling in grade 1- and first-year high school. But this will not be same number of students graduating by the end of the primary and secondary level (Macha et al.,2018). The reasons are plenty – inaccessibility of the school; lack of school facilities, lack of teachers and poverty of the family, to name a few.

A study on gender and academic performance by Mwingi, in Kenya (2014), showed that, “teachers’ negative attitudes and behaviors and time wasting among girls, more reading hours for boys, inadequate facilities, teachers’ dissatisfaction and lack of motivation in girls, irregular attendance to school by girls, low persistence and their inferiority complex were the factors for observed gender differences in the selected school in Kiambu division.” This means that even gender is a factor for not finishing school.

Table 16. Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in terms of Years and Subject involved in the NSTP Tutorial Program

Subject	Year	%	Total	%								
	2013		2014		2015		2016		2017			
English	15	12.93					12	10.34	31	26.72	58	50
Math			31	26.72	27	23.27					58	50
Total											116	100

Based on Table 16, English was taught in the years 2013, 2016 and 2017; while math was taught in 2014 and 2015.

Of the total 116 tutee-respondents, 15 (or 12.93%), 12 (or 10.34%) and 31 (or 26.72%) were taught in English. There were, on the other hand, 31 (or 26.72%) and 27 (or 23.27%) who were taught in Math. Overall, there is an equal number, 58 (or 50%), of English and Math tutee-respondents who were taught in the five-year period from 2013-2017.

Both English and Math subjects are required at the primary and secondary level. While Math is a universal subject, the English language on the other hand is considered a global language. There are, however, countries that emphasize the teaching of their own language/s rather than the English language (Ball, 2014).

The Philippines, through the Department of Education (DepEd), implemented the use of mother tongue based-multilingual education in 2012 amidst 170 languages that are spoken in the country (Llaneta, 2018).

Table 17. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Tutee-Respondents in terms of Number of Semester/s involved in the Tutorial Program

Number of Semester/s	Frequency	Percentage
1	48	41.38
2	18	15.52
3	15	12.93
4	20	17.24
5	15	12.93
Total	116	100

Table 17 shows that of the total 116 tutees: 48 (or 41.38%) joined for one semester; 18 (or 15.52%) joined for two semesters; 15 (or 12.93%) joined for three semesters; 20 (or 17.24%) joined for four semesters; and 15 (or 12.93%) joined for five semesters.

The table shows that majority of the tutees were involved in the program for one semester. Inability to comply with the requirements of the school, where the tutees are enrolled in, may help to explain this. Based on Republic Act 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, public primary and secondary education is free (Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines). However, projects may be assigned to students, transportation to and food in school are also expense items for those who go to school. Location, family and teacher factors may also help to explain school dropout.

Another plausible reason is the program's budget limitation. The NSTP Coordinator explained that it is PSBP's responsibility to choose the tutees. Funds sent by PSBP sponsors are also allocated for administrative costs. This goes to show that even non-government organizations face scarce resources.

Maximpact.com (2017) reports that there are 3.7 million non-government organizations worldwide. Common challenges they face include limited funds, strategic planning, poor governance and networking, limited technical and organizational capacity and application of non-empowering framework.

Table 18. Mean Rating of the Requirements of the Agreement from Gordon College-National Service Training Program (GC-NSTP), According to the Tutee-Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Recruits its best NSTP students to participate for the Tutorial Program	3.35	Achieved beyond expectation
2. Provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation

3. Leads the orientation of its NSTP teachers concerning the tutorial program.	3.73	Achieved beyond expectation
4. Focuses the tutorial sessions on enhancing the children's English/Math skills.	2.59	Achieved as targeted
5. Leads in the preparation of assessment tools (Pre- test and post-test that will be used in monitoring and evaluation of academic competency of sponsored children and in identifying tutorial approaches.	3.15	Achieves as targeted
6. Leads the matching of children and tutors applying the 1:1 ratio	3.98	Achieved beyond expectation
7. Provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
8. Conducts pre-test and post-test to all children participants	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
9. Leads in the identification of appropriate tutorial approach for each sponsored child using the results of pre-test and data in report cards	3.85	Achieved beyond expectation
10. Discuss the outcome of analysis and identify approaches to the NSTP tutors	3.76	Achieved beyond expectation
11. Ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
12. Requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter's sponsors	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
13. Ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home.	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
14. Requires the NSTP tutors to submit a one-page book review of the "Good Earth" to PSBP	3.94	Achieved beyond expectation
15. Ensures that the tutors will discuss " The Good Earth" to the children.	3.83	Achieved beyond expectation
16. Requires all tutors to participate in the Quiz Bee concerning the life and works of Pearl S. Buck	3.76	Achieved beyond expectation
17. Leads the evaluation of the Tutorial Program and submit a report to PSBP	3.76	Achieved beyond expectation
18. Provides technical inputs in the compliance of the different documentary requisites of the course.	3.83	Achieved beyond expectation
Overall Mean	3.75	Achieved beyond expectation

Results show that there are 18 requirements agreed upon and to be complied with by GC-NSTP. Of the 18 requirements, 16 (or 88.88%) had an adjectival rating of "achieved beyond expectation" or a numerical rating of between 3.35-4.0.

These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: "recruits its best NSTP students to participate for the Tutorial Program (3.35)"; "provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program (4.0)"; "leads the orientation of its NSTP teachers concerning the Tutorial Program (3.73)"; "leads the matching of children and tutors applying the 1:1 ratio" (3.98); "provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors" (4.0); "conducts pre-test and post-test to all children-participants" (4.0); "leads in the identification of appropriate tutorial approach for each sponsored child using the results of pre-test and data in report cards" (3.85); "discuss the outcome of analysis and identify approaches to the NSTP tutors" (3.76); "ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance" (4.0);

“requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter’s sponsors” (4.0); “ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home” (4.0); “requires the NSTP tutors to submit a one-page book review of the ‘Good Earth’ to PSBP” (3.94); “ensures that the tutors will discuss ‘The Good Earth’ to the children” (3.83); “requires all tutors to participate in the Quiz Bee concerning the life and works of Pearl S. Buck” (3.76); “leads the evaluation of the Tutorial Program and submit a report to PSBP” (3.76); “provides technical inputs in the compliance of the different documentary requisites of the course” (3.83).

Of the 18 requirements, 2 (or 11.12 %) had adjectival rating of “achieved as targeted” or a mean rating of between 2.59-3.15. These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: “focuses the tutorial sessions on enhancing the children’s English/Math skills” (2.59); and, “leads in the preparation of assessment tools (Pre- test and post-test that will be used in monitoring and evaluation of academic competency of sponsored children and in identifying tutorial approaches” (3.15).

The requirements with the highest mean rating, 4.0 or “achieved beyond expectation,” are as follows: “Provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program;” “Provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors;” “Conducts pretest and post-test to all children participants;” “Ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance;” “Requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter’s sponsors;” and “Ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home.”

Requirements with “achieved beyond expectation” are generally those which are related to the cycle of instruction. This is from needs and resource assessment to actual tutorial, monitoring of progress, evaluation and compliance to requirements of sponsors and the partner-organization, the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP)

A study by Estonanto et al., (2017) showed that grades 1-3 pupils of the Boton Elementary School in Casiguran, Sorsogon improved in their academic performance in math after they received remediation for a month. This means improving from beginners’ level, prior to the remediation, to “homogenously average and reaching proficiency level after remediation.” And this resulted after only a month of remediation.

The PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program is implemented for a semester, every year. This means five months of remediation for the tutees.

This table showing that 13 out of 18 requirements were rated by tutees as “achieved beyond expectation,” implies that GC faculty are able to meet the requirements of instruction for the tutorial program. Meeting said requirements, may therefore hopefully improve and sustain academic performance of the tutees through the PSBP-GC NSTP Tutorial Program.

Table 19. Mean Rating of the Requirements of the Agreement as expected from Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP), According to the Tutee-Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Assist GC in the orientation of NSTP teachers and students	3.59	Achieved beyond expectation

2. Gives initial orientation to children and parents regarding the Tutorial Program	3.50	Achieved beyond expectation
3. Requires all sponsored children to submit 2 copies of their report cards for the 1 st and 2 nd semesters	3.19	Achieved as targeted
4. Provides GC a copy of the children's report card	3.77	Achieved beyond expectation
5. Provides the library/NSTP department of GC with copies of "The Good Earth" novel.	3.24	Achieved as targeted
6. Monitors all tutorial sessions and sure the safety of the NSTP students and the sponsored children.	3.35	Achieved as targeted
7. Provides all sponsored children, parents and NSTP tutors during the tutorial sessions	3.82	Achieved beyond expectation
8. Provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
9. Provides transportation to all sponsored children and parents	3.74	Achieved beyond expectation
10. Assists the college in the evaluation of the Tutorial Program.	2.87	Achieved as targeted
11. Awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children.	3.96	Achieved beyond expectation
12. Awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program	3.78	Achieved beyond expectation
13. Provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program.	3.45	Achieved beyond expectation
14. Prepares feedback forms which will be answered by parents and tutors.	3.23	Achieved as targeted
15. Prepares a report based on feedback forms submitted by parents and tutors	3.60	Achieved beyond expectation
16. Submits all reports to the PSBP Board President and to the PSBP International in Pennsylvania SA.	2.78	Achieved as targeted
Overall Mean	3.49	Achieved beyond expectation

There are 16 requirements agreed upon and to be complied with by the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP). Of the 16 requirements, 11 (or 69%) had an adjectival rating of "achieved beyond expectation" or a numerical mean rating of between 3.35-4.0.

These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: "assist GC in the orientation of NSTP teachers and students (3.59); "gives initial orientation to children and parents regarding the Tutorial Program (3.50); "provides GC a copy of the children's report card" (3.77); "provides the library/NSTP department of GC with copies of 'The Good Earth' novel (3.24); "provides all sponsored children, parents and NSTP tutors during the tutorial sessions" (3.82); "provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions" (4.0); "provides transportation to all sponsored children and parents" (3.74); "awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children" (3.96); awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program (3.78); "provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program:

(3.45); “prepares a report based on feedback forms submitted by parents and tutors (3.60).

Of the 16 requirements, 5 (or 31%) had an adjectival rating of “achieved as targeted” or a numerical mean rating between 2.78-3.24. These indicators and the numerical mean rating are as follows: “requires all sponsored children to submit 2 copies of their report cards for the 1st and 2nd semesters” (2.54); “monitors all tutorial sessions and sure the safety of the NSTP students and the sponsored children” (3.35); “assists the college in the evaluation of the Tutorial Program (2.87); “prepares feedback forms which will be answered by parents and tutors” (3.23); and, “submits all reports to the PSBP Board President and to the PSBP International in Pennsylvania USA” (2.78).

The requirement with the highest mean rating, 4.0 or “achieved beyond expectation” is, “Provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions.”

Indicators with “achieved beyond expectation” are generally those which require support from the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP) with its partner-organization, Gordon College, the parents, the tutors and the tutees.

In other words, the PSBP-GC NSTP partnership does not just expect to have tutors to teach well, a process indicator, but to help produce marginalized tutees who better themselves in education. And for sustainability purpose, it is expected that the tutees, in turn, help their communities.

Results from Table 20 show that of the 39 implementer-respondents, there are 7 (or 17.94%) with ages below 20; 9 (or 23.07%) are within the 21-25 age bracket; 3 (or 7.69%) are within the 26-30 age bracket; 5 (or 12.82%) are within the 31-35 age bracket; 7 (or 17.94%) are within the 41-45 age bracket; and 3 (or 7.67%) are 46 years old or above.

Table 20. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 20 years old	7	17.94
21-25 years old	9	23.07
26-30 years old	3	7.69
31-35 years old	5	12.82
36-40 years old	5	12.82
41-45 years old	7	17.94
46 and above	3	7.67
Total	39	100

This shows that majority, 23.07%, are within the age range that is typical of new graduates and young professionals. Being young adults, they may be considered idealistic – thinking more about what they could contribute than receiving high pay. Rappler’s survey (2016) found out that millennials (age 18-35) were confident, passionate, pursuing their careers but at the same time interested to take up community causes.

Non-government organizations (NGOs), like PSBP also normally give lower salaries compared to the corporate world. This is primarily because public service is delivered. In fact, PSBP has been able to sustain its operations, for quite some time now, because of its sponsors/benefactors or civic-minded contributors.

Given this information it would appear that committed personnel of the PSBP-GC NSTP, such as the young professionals, may be more able to synchronize their own goals. That is, with that of the organization's goals of delivering public good for marginalized sectors of society.

Table 21. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	34	87.17
Male	9	12.82
Total	39	100

Results from Table 21 show that of the total 39 implementer-respondents, 34 (or 87.17%) are females; and 9 (or 12.82%) are males.

This means that there are more female, than male, implementer-respondents from both the GC and PSBP.

It has to be understood, however, that non-government organizations sprouted along with the world's experience of discrimination, exploitation, marginalization, oppression and subordination. This is along with the improvements in wealth, tax reforms and the onset of the internet age.

In other words, unequal relationships (gender-related or human rights-related) may continue to see NGOs serving those who are discriminated, violated and in need.

Table 22. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	24	61.53
Married	15	38.46
Total	39	100

Results from Table 22 show that of the total 39 implementer-respondents, 24 (or 61.53%) are single and 15 (or 38.46%) are married. This means that majority are single.

Philippine Statistics data show that poverty among sectors in 2006, 2009, 2012 and 2015 have not reduced much (Albert & Raymundo, 2016). Farmers and fisherfolks, the economic backbones of the country, had the highest incidence-34.3% and 34% respectively. This is in terms of being impoverished in 2015. Incidence of poverty among the youth was approximately 21.1% for the same period. While urban residents' poverty incidence is an average 12.4% for the same period, according to the same report.

Analyzing, somebody who is single may have more opportunity to develop careers, improve income, even spend for travel and leisure as compared to a married person.

Females, are especially, more likely to be tied up with her spouse and children once she decides to tie the knot.

Table 23. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Residence

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Olongapo City	23	58.97
Zambales	8	20.51
Bataan	3	7.69
Manila	4	10.25
Pampanga	1	2.56
Total	39	100

Results from Table 23 show that of the total 39 implementers, 23 (or 58.97%) are from Olongapo City; 8 (or 20.51%) are from Zambales; 3 (or 7.69%) are from Bataan; 4 (or 10.25%) are from Manila; and 1 (or 2.56%) is from Pampanga.

This shows that majority of the respondents are from Olongapo City. The partnership between GC and the PSBP is primarily to make GC NSTP to tutor indigent children in Olongapo City. GC is based in Olongapo City and the NSTP is implemented in the area. It is therefore expected to have implementers including participants of the program to reside or live nearby the area. This addresses the issue of accessibility but more especially the effectivity of the program.

A study by Ellah and Ita (2017), on the relationship between school location and student's academic performance in English, found out that there is significant difference between the two variables. Meaning, the nearer the school is, the higher the academic performance of the students. The study area is in Nigeria.

In the PSBP-GC NSTP partnership, indigent children are transported from their residence to the college and are provided snacks for the duration of their review. Some parents of the same children are assigned as coordinators who provide administrative support.

Accessibility is critical to fast response to needs that arise from the program cycle. Effectivity, on the other hand, is critical to understanding the concerns, interests and context of the program beneficiaries.

Table 24. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Ethnicity

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
Indigenous	5	12.82
Non-indigenous	34	87.17
Total	39	100

Results from Table 24 show that of the total 39 respondents, 5 (or 12.82%) are indigenous and 34 (or 87.17%) are non-indigenous.

This means that majority of the respondent-implementers are non-indigenous. It is worth noting that indigenous persons/peoples/communities used to be called "minorities." They

are peoples who, having chosen to retain much of their culture, are denigrated and discriminated for this choice and for the small number of their group (RA 8371). This is, as compared to the number of Christians, in the country, who have been converted through the Spanish occupation.

Program implementers with a background as diverse as the beneficiaries is actually positive as it facilitates understanding on how to run the program. Gupta (2013) argues in her thesis that, “Overall workforce diversity enhances better decision- making, higher creativity, innovation, greater success in marketing, better distribution of economic opportunity & competitive advantage. Moreover, the study also reveals that senior management accountability, need assessment, better strategy, efficient communication, team building & evaluation act as mediators between work force diversity & performance.” A world that is linked by the worldwide web has been increasing communication flow. It, in return, may result to stiffer competition. A diverse workforce may therefore facilitate better understanding.

Results from Table 25 show that of the total 39 respondents, 3 (or 7.69%) are Master’s graduate; 1 (or 2.56%) are Master’s level; 6 (or 15.38%) are college graduate; 20 (or 51.28%) are college level; 7 (or 17.94%) are high school graduates; and 2 (or 5.12%) are high school level.

Similar to the findings from Table 20, Table 22 shows the diversity of stakeholders (implementers) involved in the PSBP-GC NSTP Program. This is in terms of age, residence, sex, civil status, and ethnicity.

Table 25. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Master’s graduate	3	7.69
Master’s level	1	2.56
College graduate	6	15.38
College level	20	51.28
High school graduate	7	17.94
High school level	2	5.12
Total	39	100

Diversity maximizes the output from participation. This is because it allows the organization to benefit from mindsets coming from stakeholders with diverse backgrounds. Meaning, it is more likely that critical factors are exhaustively considered in the program.

A study titled *Stakeholder Participation and Utilization in Program Evaluation* (Greene, 1988) classified stakeholders of two programs into categories: very involved persons; sometimes/somewhat involved persons, and marginally involved persons. It found out that “Within the cognitive-process dimension, the repeated opportunities to discuss, reflect on, and process evaluation information appeared to underlie the strong conceptual

benefits of participation itself and, in turn, enhanced stakeholder understanding of the evaluation findings.”

On the affective aspect, on the other hand, an enhanced understanding of the programs were observed at the theoretical level. More important, however, was the finding that the programs gained “higher credibility” and “persuasiveness.”

Table 26. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Implementer-Respondents in terms of Number of Semester/s Involved in the Tutorial Program

Number of Semesters	Frequency	Percentage
1	20	51.28
2	2	5.12
3	3	7.69
4	5	12.82
5	9	23.07
Total	39	100

Results from Table 26 show that of the total of 39 implementers, 20 (or 51.28%) were involved for one semester; two (or 5.12%) were involved for two semesters; three (or 7.69%) were involved for three semesters; five (or 12.82%) were involved for four semesters; and nine (or 23.07%) were involved for five semesters.

This means that majority of the respondents were involved in at least one semester. Implementers include the NSTP coordinator and parent coordinators who provide administrative support every 2nd semester when NSTP 102 is offered. Unlike NSTP 101, a prerequisite for NSTP 102, the former is lecture-type. It orients the tutors on the program, its components, and the community. NSTP 102, on the other hand, applies what were learned in NSTP 101 class, i.e., in a host community.

The PSBP-GC NSTP Program implements the literacy component for indigenous students of Olongapo. Through the partnership, PSBP selects tutees based on their sponsorship program. GC-NSTP, on the other hand, readies the tutors, coordinators, facilities and other administrative requirements during the 2nd semester.

There is only one NSTP coordinator and a few parent-coordinators. Availability of both, but especially the latter, may help to explain the limited number of semester (one) of involvement. Coordinatorship is a voluntary rather than a full-time and regularly-compensated work.

The need for program sustainability may be assumed from this data. Clarification on this data showed that the NSTP coordinator provided supervision for five consecutive semesters. Parent-coordinator, with more interest to pursue the success of the program, were at hand to assist the NSTP coordinator. Without these implementers, continuous improvement may be more difficult.

Table 27. Mean Rating of the Requirements of the Agreement from Gordon College-National Service Training Program (GC-NSTP), According to the Implementer-Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
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1. Recruits its best NSTP students to participate for the Tutorial Program	3.51	Achieved beyond expectation
2. Provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
3. Leads the orientation of its NSTP teachers concerning the tutorial program.	3.84	Achieved beyond expectation
4. Focuses the tutorial sessions on enhancing the children's English/Math skills.	3.84	Achieved beyond expectation
5. Leads in the preparation of assessment tools (Pre- test and post-test that will be used in monitoring and evaluation of academic competency of sponsored children and in identifying tutorial approaches.	3.97	Achieved beyond expectation
6. Leads the matching of children and tutors applying the 1:1 ratio	3.76	Achieved beyond expectation
7. Provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors	3.94	Achieved beyond expectation
8. Conducts pre test and post-test to all children participants	3.64	Achieved beyond expectation
9. Leads in the identification of appropriate tutorial approach for each sponsored child using the results of pre-test and data in report cards	3.58	Achieved beyond expectation
10. Discuss the outcome of analysis and identify approaches to the NSTP tutors	3.20	Achieved as targeted
11. Ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance	3.87	Achieved beyond expectation
12. Requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter's sponsors	3.61	Achieved beyond expectation
13. Ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home.	3.51	Achieved beyond expectation
14. Requires the NSTP tutors to submit a one-page book review of the "Good Earth" to PSBP	3.51	Achieved beyond expectation
15. Ensures that the tutors will discuss "The Good Earth" to the children.	3.25	Achieved as targeted
16. Requires all tutors to participate in the Quiz Bee concerning the life and works of Pearl S. Buck	3.64	Achieved beyond expectation
17. Leads the evaluation of the Tutorial Program and submit a report to PSBP	3.48	Achieved beyond expectation
18. Provides technical inputs in the compliance of the different documentary requisites of the course.	3.69	Achieved beyond expectation
Overall Mean	3.66	Achieved beyond expectation

Results show that there are 18 requirements agreed upon and to be complied with by the Gordon College-National Service Training Program (GC-NSTP). Of the 18 requirements, 16 (or 89%) garnered an adjectival rating of "achieved beyond expectation" or a numerical rating of between 3.48-4.0.

These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: "recruits its best NSTP students to participate for the Tutorial Program (3.51)"; "provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program (4.0)"; "leads the orientation of its NSTP teachers concerning the Tutorial Program (3.84)"; "focuses the tutorial sessions on enhancing the children's English/Math

skills” (3.84); “leads in the preparation of assessment tools (Pre- test and post-test that will be used in monitoring and evaluation of academic competency of sponsored children and in identifying tutorial approaches: (3.97); “leads the matching of children and tutors applying the 1:1 ratio” (3.76); “provides pre-orientation to NSTP tutors” (3.94); “conducts pre-test and post-test to all children-participants” (3.64); “leads in the identification of appropriate tutorial approach for each sponsored child using the results of pre-test and data in report cards” (3.58); “ensures that the NSTP students are regularly monitored in terms of performance” (3.78)); “requires NSTP tutors to assist the children in the preparation of letters and Christmas cards for the latter’s sponsors” (3.61); “ensures that all children will be given homework/assignments so that they can continue their learning at home” (3.51); “requires the NSTP tutors to submit a one-page book review of the ‘Good Earth’ to PSBP” (3.51); “requires all tutors to participate in the Quiz Bee concerning the life and works of Pearl S. Buck” (3.64); “leads the evaluation of the Tutorial Program and submit a report to PSBP” (3.48); “provides technical inputs in the compliance of the different documentary requisites of the course” (3.69).

Of the 18 requirements, 2 (or 11%) had adjectival rating of “achieved as targeted” or a mean rating of between 3.20-3.25. These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: “discuss the outcome of analysis and identify approaches to the NSTP tutors” (3.20); and “ensures that the tutors will discuss ‘The Good Earth’ to the children” (3.25). Garnering the highest mean rating of 4.0 or “achieved beyond expectation” is the requirement, “Provides the venue and facilities for the tutorial program.” This implies that a conducive learning environment is a factor for better performance.

All other requirements with “achieved beyond expectation” mean rating refer to the terms of agreement between Gordon College and Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP) so that the National Service Training Program, through the Tutorial Program, could be of quality.

Quality of programs are raised up depending on a lot of factors including planning. This includes appropriate performance indicators utilized. In this case, it means undertaking tasks assigned to stakeholders and the quality of facilities and instruction.

Table 28. Mean Rating of the Requirements as expected from the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP), According to the Implementer-Respondents

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Assist GC in the orientation of NSTP teachers and students	3.41	Achieved beyond expectation
2. Gives initial orientation to children and parents regarding the Tutorial Program	3.53	Achieved beyond expectation
3. Requires all sponsored children to submit 2 copies of their report cards for the 1 st and 2 nd semesters	3.10	Achieved as targeted
4. Provides GC a copy of the children’s report card	2.82	Achieved as targeted
5. Provides the library/NSTP department of GC with copies of “The Good Earth” novel.	3.61	Achieved beyond expectation
6. Monitors all tutorial sessions and sure the safety of the NSTP students and the sponsored children.	3.51	Achieved beyond expectation
7. Provides all sponsored children, parents and NSTP tutors during the tutorial sessions	3.46	Achieved beyond expectation

8. Provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
9. Provides transportation to all sponsored children and parents	3.12	Achieved as targeted
10. Assists the college in the evaluation of the Tutorial Program.	3.28	Achieved as targeted
11. Awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children.	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
12. Awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program	4.00	Achieved beyond expectation
13. Provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program.	3.97	Achieved beyond expectation
14. Prepares feedback forms which will be answered by parents and tutors.	3.89	Achieved beyond expectation
15. Prepares a report based on feedback forms submitted by parents and tutors	3.58	Achieved beyond expectation
16. Submits all reports to the PSBP Board President and to the PSBP International in Pennsylvania USA.	3.61	Achieved beyond expectation
Overall Mean	3.56	Achieved beyond expectation

There are 16 requirements agreed upon and to be complied with by the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP). Of the 16 requirements, 14 (or 88%) had an adjectival rating of “achieved beyond expectation” or a numerical mean rating of between 3.41-4.0.

These requirements and the mean ratings are as follows: “assist GC in the orientation of NSTP teachers and students (3.41); “gives initial orientation to children and parents regarding the Tutorial Program (3.53); “provides GC a copy of the children’s report card” (2.82); “monitors all tutorial sessions and ensure the safety of the NSTP students and the sponsored children” (3.51); “assists the college in the evaluation of the Tutorial Program (3.28); “prepares feedback forms which will be answered by parents and tutors” (3.89); and, “submits all reports to the PSBP Board President and to the PSBP International in Pennsylvania USA” (2.78); “provides the library/NSTP department of GC with copies of ‘The Good Earth’ novel (3.61); “provides all sponsored children, parents and NSTP tutors during the tutorial sessions” (3.46); “provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors during tutorial sessions” (4.0); “awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children” (4.0); awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program (4.0); “provides certificates to all children and tutors that will participate in the program: (3.97); “prepares a report based on feedback forms submitted by parents and tutors (3.58).

Of the 16 requirements, 2 (or 12%) had an adjectival rating of “achieved as targeted” or a numerical mean rating between 3.10-3.12. These requirements and the numerical mean rating are as follows: “requires all sponsored children to submit 2 copies of their report cards for the 1st and 2nd semesters” (3.10); “provides transportation to all sponsored children and parents’ (3.12);

Garnering the highest mean rate of 4.0 or “achieved beyond expectation are the following requirements: “Provides snacks to sponsored children, selected parents and NSTP tutors

during tutorial sessions;" "Awards medals to NSTP students that will demonstrate exemplary performance in fulfilling their responsibilities to the children;" and "Awards medals to children that will demonstrate noticeable progress as a result of the Tutorial Program." These requirements show consistency with the response of tutors and tutees showing that the basic need of food and recognition are necessary for program success; and that in this case, the expectations from the same indicators have been successfully met.

Overall, indicators with an "achieved beyond expectation" rating refer to tasks that need to be undertaken by the Pearl S. Buck Foundation of the Philippines (PSBP) as a partner of Gordon College, i.e., for the NSTP Tutorial Program. It may be gleaned from the indicators that the financial requirements of the program are expected to be delivered by PSBP, while GC provides the technical expertise. In this case, PSBP was able to deliver results with 14 out of 16 indicators accomplished in the five-year period, according to the implementer-respondents.

Effective partnerships go beyond the terms of agreements. This is because neither institution is even corporate and, therefore, has limited resources. Nevertheless, any risk may be managed if a lot of the elements that make a quality partnership exist or if partners ensure that they deliver their end of the bargain.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that most college students fall within the young adulthood stage of Erikson's theory of human development, with a notable gender disparity favoring female students over their male counterparts. Furthermore, most tertiary students exhibited normal height, weight, and BMI, while the College of Education, Arts, and Sciences accounted for most respondents. Interestingly, when college students were grouped by age and height, no significant differences were identified in the factors influencing physical wellness. However, it was evident that various factors, including exercise, substance use, diet, lifestyle choices, and access to medical care, played a significant role in shaping the physical wellness of college students. Contrary to the null hypothesis, the study's results indicated that significant differences did exist in these factors when students were categorized based on sex, weight, BMI, and academic department, shedding light on important distinctions in the physical wellness experiences of college students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to foster a culture of holistic well-being among tertiary students, it is imperative that Gordon College, in collaboration with local government units and non-government organizations, organizes orientation and awareness programs. These initiatives should educate students on the significance of regular exercise in promoting a healthy lifestyle. Additionally, there is a pressing need to continually disseminate nutritional information, emphasizing the pivotal role of diet in providing the requisite strength and energy for active engagement both within and outside the educational institution. Furthermore, the school administration and college departments should jointly conduct orientation sessions

to raise awareness about the importance of medical care, encouraging students to seek healthcare when faced with health issues proactively. Lastly, to enhance our comprehension of the wellness factors affecting college students, further research endeavors should be undertaken to validate results and refine our understanding of this crucial facet of student life.

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